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2 йўналиш: ГЛОБАЛ ИҚТИСОДИЙ ВА ТАЪЛИМНИНГ РАҚАМЛИ ИҚТИСОДИЙЛАРИ
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MUNDARIJA

“Yashil” iqtisodiyotga jadal o‘tish va barqaror texnologik o‘zgarishlar provard maqsadlarimiz	12
Abduraxmonova Gulnora Kalandarovna	
Noqonuniy sigaretalar hajmini Empty pack survey hamda Gap analysis usullari yordamida aniqlash (O‘zbekiston Respublikasi misolida)	17
Sanjar Mirzaliev, Bobur Qoraboev, Surmaniso Mirzalieva	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida bank xizmat turlarini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	22
A. R. Norov, N. N. Norova	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot rivojida tijorat banklari kapitalini takomillashtirish istiqbollari	28
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich	
Ishsizlik darajasini kamaytirish yo‘lidagi strategik yondashuv: tadbirkorlikka o‘rgatish va kasbiy tayyorlash	33
Bakiyeva Iroda Akbarovna, Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich	
Meva-sabzavot mahsulotlarini eksportga yo‘naltirishda standart talablariga uyg‘unlashtirishni baholash va uni amalga oshirish yo‘llari	42
Xojiyev Elshod Yoqub o‘g‘li	
Investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda foyda solig‘idan foydalanish	50
Zarif Oripovich Axrorov	
Mamlakat iqtisodiy o‘shish va rivojlanishida xorijiy investitsiyalarning roli	55
Akishova Shaxnoza Davlet qizi	
O‘zbekiston sharoitida “yashil” iqtisodiyotni joriy etish istiqbollari: nazariya va amaliyot.....	60
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o‘g‘li	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlari faoliyatini takomillashtirish yo‘nalishlari.....	65
Sadikova Muslima Alisher qizi	
Mehnat bozorida aholi bandligini oshirishning zamonaviy usullari	70
Xuvaydullaeva Iroda Xusniddin qizi	
Ichki turizmni rivojlantirishning tashkiliy mexanizmining asosiy prinsiplari	76
Isomiddinov Inomjon Qurbonali o‘g‘li	
Yengil sanoat korxonalarida ichki audit jarayonlari va uning samaradorligini oshirish istiqbollari.....	79
Maxmudov A.N.	
Ishlab chiqarish resurslaridan foydalangan holda korporativ boshqaruv tizimini takomillashtirish	86
Karimov Akramjon Ikromjon o‘g‘li	
Kredit foiz stavkalari va unga ta‘sir etuvchi omillar tahlili.....	92
Orifova Dilnoza Obid qizi	
O‘zbekistonda hayot sug‘urtasini rivojlantirish yo‘llari	97
Jamolova Xonzoda O‘rolboy qizi	
Soliqqa Tortishning Mohiyati va Uni Iqtisodiyotdagi Ahamiyati.....	102
Ruziyev Shaxzod Behzod o‘g‘li, Togayev Salim Sobirovich	
Raqamli texnologiyalarning oziq-ovqat sanoatini rivojlantirishdagi ta‘siri	110
Abduraxmanova Zuxra Toxir qizi	
O‘zbekistonda sog‘lomlashtirish turizmini rivojlantirishda inson resurslarining o‘rni.....	115
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna	
Biznes jarayonlarining samaradorligini baholash ko‘rsatkichlarini muvofiqlashtirish usullari.....	121
Abdusalomova Nodira Baxodirovna	

Turizmda inson resurslarini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	126
J. Mansurov	
Hududiy turizm rivojlanishining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirishda zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarini qo'llanilishi.....	131
Dustmurodov Orifjon Ismatilloevich	
Aholi ixtiyoridagi resurslarni jalb qilish orqali aholi turmush darajasini oshirish.....	138
Jo'raeva Shahlo Uchqun qizi	
Turistik xizmatlarning samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish.....	141
Abduvohidov Abdumalik Mahkamovich	
Xo'jalik subyektlarining moliyaviy salohiyatini mustahkamlash va moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlashni uslubiy jihatlari.....	146
Xasanov Baxodir Akramovich, Akramov G'olibjon Bahodir o'g'li	
Mahsulot raqobatbardoshligini baholash usullari va ulardan foydalanish muammolari.....	153
Onorboev Sh.M.	
Loyihalarni Islom modeli asosida moliyalashtirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	159
Aminova Nilufar Umarboy qizi	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklarida foiz riskini boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish.....	167
Isakov Janabay Yakipbaevich	
Ayollar inson kapitalini rivojlantirishning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	174
S.A.Bozorova, M.M.Xolmatov	
Qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarini yaratish bilan bog'liq loyihalarni moliyalashtirish.....	179
Shaislamova Nargiza Kabilovna	
Effectiveness of using blockchain technologies in cash flow audit in enterprises of the republic of Uzbekistan.....	188
Atamurodov Saidmurad Yakhyoyevich	
Loan portfolio of banks in Uzbekistan and ways to improve the efficiency of loan portfolio management.....	196
Avazkhon Agzamov, Dilrabo Malikova	
Digitization of the economy and its role in enhancing bank stability and reducing poverty.....	201
Kholiyorov Murod Kahramon ugli, Kholiyorova Shokhista Kahramon kizi	
Directions for sustainable development of tourism in the namangan region of Uzbekistan.....	204
Khusniddin Egamnazarov	
Improving comprehensive monitoring of cash flows in the treasury through intelligent information fusion systems applications.....	208
Shodmonkulova Shahlo	
Importance of staff service quality at uzbek halal restaurants in Uzbekistan.....	214
Shodiyona Sanginova	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida barqaror turizmni iqtisodiy rivojlantirishda hunarmandchilikning o'rni.....	220
Xushnazarova Maxzuna Gulamdjanovna	
Mamlakat turizmini barqaror rivojlanishida mice turizmining ahamiyati.....	226
Xalimova Fayyoza Nafasovna	
Ways to expand the position of the light industrial enterprise in the yarn and knitwear market.....	231
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Agzamov Avazkhon Talgatovich	
Improvement of methodology of accounting and analysis of included financial statements and investments in subsidiary societies.....	238
Nasirkhodjaeva Dilafruz Sabitkhanovna	

Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida investitsiyalar: barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishning muhim omili.....	254
Amonova Nazokat Utkurovna	
O'zbekiston respublikasi korxonalarida pul oqimlari auditida blokchain texnologiyalaridan foydalanish samaradorligi.....	259
Atamurodov Saidmurod Yaxyoyevich	
Iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish sharoitida o'zbekistonda turizm xizmatlar iste'molini oshirishning ekonometrik tahlili	267
Dehqonov Burxon Rustamovich	
Agrar soha korxonalarining moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlash masalalari.....	278
Erkinxojiyev I.	
Yengil sanoat korxonalarida marketing jarayonlarini tashkil etishning xorij tajribasi	283
Bazarova Fayoza Tuxtamurodovna	
Fiskal siyosatni rivojlantirishda "yashil" budjet daromadlarini o'rganish.....	287
Meyliyev O.R., Gofurova K.	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot: raqamli transformatsiyaning yashil shaharlarning iqtisodiy o'sishiga ta'siri.....	293
Xotamov Ibodulla, Najmiddinov Yahyo	
Buxoro viloyatining kichik va o'rta biznesdagi o'rni, viloyatdagi tumanlar faoliyatidan kelib chiqib hududlarni toifalarga ajratish.....	301
Bozorov Ilyos Isomiddinovich	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda ishlab chiqarishning optimal hajmi tahlili	306
Qlichev Baxtiyor Pardaevich, Xoldorov Sardor Umarovich	
Toshkent viloyati fermer xo'jaliklari faoliyatining samaradorligini tanlanma kuzatuvlar asosida statistik tadqiq etish	313
Murodov Jahongir Choriyevich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida sanoat tarmog'i faoliyati samaradorligini statistik baholashning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	316
To'raeva Zilola Turg'unovna	
"Yashil" sanoat siyosati – ekologik xavfsizlikni ta'minlashning ustuvor vositasi	320
Muqimov Sherali Axmadali o'g'li	
Raqamli biznes marketingida yashil buxgalteriya hisobining roli: barqaror rivojlanish nuqtai nazaridan qarash.....	327
Allayarov Shamsiddin Amanullayevich, Iskandarov Xurshid Iskandarovich, Yoqubov Madaminbek Abdurahim o'g'li	
Fiskal barqarorlikni ta'minlashda "natijaga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirish" uslubidan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	333
Kasimova Gulyar Axmatovna, Agzamov Avazxon Talgatovich	
Регулирование занятости и управление трудовыми ресурсами в сфере туризма.....	339
Адылова Зулфия Джавдатовна, Тухтаева Хуршида Фарходовна	
Семь IPO и SPO в экономической истории узбекистана: достижения, проблемы и выводы	346
Чинкулов Кахрамон Равшанович	
Совершенствование учета затрат на производство и калькуляция себестоимости продукции	355
Омонов Шердор Ойбек угли	
Areas of effective use of marketing in the development of foreign economic relations	360
Akhmedov Ikram Akramovich	
Sanoatda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashning iqtisodiy masalalari	367
Ismoilova Gulchiroy Tolliboy qizi	

Hududlarni iqtisodiy rivojlanishida investitsiyalar ko'rsatkichi tahlili (Sirdaryo viloyati misolida)	373
Karimqulov Jasur Imomboyevich, Alimova Dilafro'z Tohir qizi	
Raqamli transformatsiya davridagi iqtisodiy o'sishga to'rtinchi sanoat inqilobining ta'siri.....	381
Mirxamidova Zahinabonu Mirxamid qizi	
Investitsion muhit va uning hududlarni iqtisodiyot va ijtimoiy rivojlanishdagi ahamiyati.....	388
Muxamadjanov Shaxriyor Solidjon o'g'li	
Portfel investisiya loyihalarini kreditlashni takomillashtirish.....	395
Ibragimov Gafurjan Axmetovich	
O'zbekistonda kapital bozorini rivojlantirish masalalari	401
Turdieva Uzayda Omirbaevna	
Korxonalarining tashqi savdo faoliyatini rivojlantirishda tijorat banklari faolligini oshirish yo'llari.....	408
Ibragimov Mansur Axmetovich	
Methodological foundations of the quality management system in construction industry enterprises.....	414
Usmanov Ilkhom Achilovich, Buriyev Xakim Toshimovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligini rivojlantirish jarayonini ekonometrik modellashtirishda xorijiy davlatlar tajribasining ahamiyati.....	419
Butanova Dilnoza Rustamovna	
O'zbekistonda qishloq turizmini rivojlantirishda Janubiy Koreya tajribasini o'rganish.....	423
Agzamova Nargiza Gapurovna	
Kimyo sanoatiga innovatsiyalarni joriy etish bo'yicha rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasi.....	427
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Концептуальные основы и перспективы развития деятельности кадастровых служб республики узбекистан на основе интеллектуальных технологий	430
М.К. Валиев, А.Х. Абдуллаев, А.Р. Марахимов, Б.М. Ахмедов	
Mahalliy avtomobil benzini tarkibidagi uglevodorod fraksiyalariga ekstragentlarining ta'sirini o'rganish	435
Maxmudov Muxtor Jamolovich, Murtazaev Feruzbek Ismatovich	
Oliy ta'lim muassalaridagi davlat xaridlari tizimining takomillashishi.....	441
Atamuratova Nilufar Yaxshigeldiyevna	
Tijorat banki daromadlari – moliyaviy barqarorlikning omili sifatida.....	446
Umarov Davron Shavkatovich	

AREAS OF EFFECTIVE USE OF MARKETING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF FOREIGN ECONOMIC RELATIONS

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Abstract: This article examines scientific views related to the use of marketing in the development of foreign economic relations. The impact of marketing on the formation of foreign market conditions, the importance of marketing in the organization, management, and control of foreign economic activities of companies is analyzed. The methods of assessing the competitiveness of companies in foreign economic activity have been studied. The impact of factors affecting competitiveness is analyzed, and their importance in increasing the country's export potential is substantiated.

Key words: foreign economic activity, marketing, international marketing, competition, competitiveness, factors affecting competitiveness, competitive advantage, export potential, diversification.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tashqi iqtisodiy aloqalarni rivojlantirishda marketingdan foydalanishga oid ilmiy qarashlar o'rganilgan. Marketingning tashqi bozor sharoitlarini shakllantirishdagi ta'siri, shuningdek, korxonalarning tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyatini tashkil etish, boshqarish va nazorat qilishdagi ahamiyati tahlil qilingan. Korxonalarning tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyatda raqobatbardoshligini baholash usullari o'rganilgan. Raqobatbardoshlikka ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlil qilinib, ularning mamlakatning eksport salohiyatini oshirishdagi ahamiyati asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyat, marketing, xalqaro marketing, raqobat, raqobatbardoshlik, raqobatbardoshlikka ta'sir etuvchi omillar, raqobat ustunligi, eksport salohiyati, diversifikatsiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются научные взгляды на использование маркетинга в развитии внешнеэкономических связей. Проанализировано влияние маркетинга на формирование условий внешнего рынка, а также его значение в организации, управлении и контроле внешнеэкономической деятельности компаний. Изучены методы оценки конкурентоспособности компаний, занимающихся внешнеэкономической деятельностью. Анализируются факторы, влияющие на конкурентоспособность, и обоснована их значимость в повышении экспортного потенциала страны.

Ключевые слова: внешнеэкономическая деятельность, маркетинг, международный маркетинг, конкуренция, конкурентоспособность, факторы, влияющие на конкурентоспособность, конкурентное преимущество, экспортный потенциал, диверсификация.

INTRODUCTION

Strengthening foreign economic activity for economic entities of our republic, along with deepening integration into the global economic system, is of urgent importance. In particular, the 28th goal of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated January 28, 2022, No. PF-60, "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026," is to increase the export volume of the republic to 30 billion US dollars by 2026 through enhancing the export potential of the country. This goal aims to continue the active support system for exporting enterprises and to further develop the export potential of local industries by fully utilizing existing opportunities. It is determined that introducing standards that meet foreign market and international requirements, as well as attracting renowned brands, is a demand of the times [1].

Achieving this goal involves attracting foreign investors and managers to local production enterprises for their active participation in corporate management, modernization of production, technical and technological upgrades, and the organization of high-quality, competitive product manufacturing for export to foreign markets. This brings to the agenda the need to increase the effectiveness of measures aimed at significantly reducing state participation in the economy by creating favorable conditions, reducing state assets, and decreasing state shares in the authorized capital of joint-stock companies. In addressing these tasks, it is essential to study the impact of international marketing on foreign economic activity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Foreign economic relations, especially issues related to increasing the competitiveness of various sectors of the national economy, have been widely explored in the scientific research of numerous foreign scholars. In addition to general issues regarding the organization of marketing within enterprises, these scholars have studied various aspects of marketing in foreign economic activity.

They also examined the theoretical foundations of specific areas of international and national marketing, particularly problems associated with doing business in the international market. Here, we will discuss a few key examples.

For instance, American economist M. Porter highlighted that companies' entry into foreign markets is relatively complex. The optimal selection of methods for entering foreign markets requires the elimination, or at least reduction, of potential risks. While encouraging national companies to engage in international business, he identified three main aspects of international marketing relations: trade expansion, resource procurement, and diversification of trade sources [2]. In this context, he also emphasized the forms of capital movement, the costs of entering foreign markets, and the aspects of investment attractiveness when operating internationally.

Russian economist M. Galushko noted that utilizing mutual cooperation among companies in foreign economic relations can yield economic benefits. According to international marketing practices, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) can compete with large corporations by supplying the foreign market with high-quality products at relatively lower prices. His conceptual strategy for international production cooperation aims to strengthen the competitive advantage of a company by selectively leveraging the competitive strengths of foreign partners, ultimately achieving a synergistic effect [3].

British economists Pervez Gauri and Philip Cateora noted that positive changes in international economic relations, as well as the globalization and integration of national economies, have contributed to the increased significance of international marketing [4].

American economists K. Hacksever, B. Render, and R. Russell note that there are several interrelated tools in international marketing, including marketing research, product policy, sales channels, advertising, and service [5]. These tools determine a company's marketing strategy, and their effectiveness directly correlates with the company's success in foreign markets. These marketing tools aim to facilitate communication between the foreign customer and the company.

American economists D. Schultz and F. Kichen emphasize the importance of a company's image in foreign market performance. In foreign markets, a company can penetrate new territories with a high-value trade brand and develop specific marketing strategies for each region. With the rapid changes in the global economic system, consumers perceive the trade brand as a significant value, and it has become the "key" to integrated marketing [6].

American economists R. Nilemegam and P. Chintagunta have demonstrated that modern technologies, particularly information and communication technologies, are becoming influential factors in international marketing [7].

While such studies provide an essential scientific and methodological foundation, there has been a lack of research in Uzbekistan on the foreign economic potential of national enterprises and the effective application of international marketing methods in enhancing export activities. It is of scientific and practical importance to develop practical recommendations proposed by the author on entering foreign markets and increasing the export potential of national companies, considering the current state of the economy, future development trends, modernization of enterprises, and technical-technological re-equipment.

Russian economists N. Lyasnikov and Yu. Lyasnikov highlight the complexity of international marketing, a process associated with the movement of goods and services across countries. They argue that international marketing is characterized by the formation of national production based on foreign market conditions, specialization of countries, and the organization of foreign economic and trade activities by various companies, as well as the centralization of management and control [8]. The globalization of the world economy strengthens the international specialization of countries and regional structures, promoting the mutual exchange of goods and services.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research problem was selected based on the significant tasks outlined in the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2021. The inductive approach was chosen for the study, and the research problem was examined using methods of economic analysis, logical reasoning, scientific abstraction, and the grouping of scientific knowledge. The theoretical and methodological foundation of the research is built on the scientific works of both foreign and domestic scholars.

It also explores the theoretical underpinnings of international and national marketing in foreign economic activities, as well as issues related to conducting business in the international market.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In international marketing, several interrelated tools play a crucial role, including marketing research, brand policy, sales channels, advertising, and customer service. These tools shape a company's marketing policy, and their effectiveness directly determines the company's success in foreign markets. These marketing tools are primarily focused on ensuring effective communication between the foreign customer and the company.

In international marketing, it is essential to organize production to meet the multifaceted and ever-growing global demand while ensuring the simultaneous delivery of goods to various parts of the world. This approach reflects the dynamics of the market, yet it also gives rise to new challenges due to its complexity and the contradictions inherent in global trade. As the quantity and variety of goods produced increase, so does the need for resources. Although resource scarcity posed a serious threat to economic growth by the 1990s, enhanced cooperation between nations led to greater alignment within their economic integration structures.

This environment facilitates the entry of national companies into foreign markets. The process of entering foreign markets can be accomplished through several methods, which are outlined in the diagram (Picture 1).

Picture 1. Foreign market entry methods of national companies¹.

The organization of foreign economic activities of companies involves selecting appropriate methods for entering the foreign market. Specific indicators of foreign market entry include:

- Forms of capital movement (export, cooperation, transfer, joint venture, ownership);
- The amount of expenses related to entering the foreign country's market;
- The level of investment attractiveness.

In the Asia-Pacific integration processes, Japan is increasingly important as a source of financing, management experience, and technology, both now and in the future. However, it is crucial for Japan to maintain its global leadership in product innovation and production technologies. While rising competition from China, South Korea, and other countries may reduce Japan's share in world trade, Japan is expected to retain its global leadership in high-value-added industries, especially in the production and export of machinery products.

In Uzbekistan, efforts are being made to secure a strong position in foreign markets by introducing new management systems in enterprises and actively utilizing international marketing tools. Emphasis is placed on the production of competitive, high-quality, exportable finished goods by domestic manufacturers, with foreign investments facilitating the implementation of modern techniques and technologies.

In line with the 26th goal of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022, No. PF-60, "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026," the country aims to further improve its investment environment and increase its attractiveness. Over the next five years, Uzbekistan plans to attract \$120 billion in investments, including \$70 billion in foreign investments. A new system based on the "bottom-up" principle will be introduced to ensure effective use of investments and to increase export volumes.

Moreover, the strategy aims to attract \$14 billion in investments in key sectors such as energy, transport, healthcare, education, ecology, public utilities, water management, and others through public-private partnerships by 2026.

¹ Source: author development.

A similar trend is observed in the export of non-ferrous metals, energy resources, petroleum products, and transportation services. Meanwhile, gold, food products, services, and machinery and equipment are gaining prominence, gradually replacing the declining share of these sectors in the overall export structure of our country.

Picture 2. Foreign trade of Uzbekistan in 2023³.

3 Source: <https://review.uz/oz/post/infografika-vneshnyaya-torgovlya-uzbekistana>

In January-December 2023, foreign trade turnover in Uzbekistan amounted to 62.6 billion dollars and increased by 12.1 billion dollars or 23.9% compared to the same period of 2022. This was revealed from the preliminary data of the Statistical Agency of the country.

From the total trade turnover, exports amounted to 24.4 billion dollars (an increase of 23.8% as of January-December 2023), and imports amounted to 38.1 billion dollars (an increase of 24%). As a result, the balance of foreign trade turned out to be negative and amounted to 13.7 billion dollars.

Today, Uzbekistan has established trade relations with 198 countries of the world. The largest volume of trade turnover was recorded with China (21.9%). Next is Russia with 15.8%.

Foreign trade turnover of Uzbekistan with CIS countries reached 20.6 billion dollars. Out of this, the export volume was 8.1 billion dollars, and the import volume was 12.4 billion dollars.

Picture 3. Top-5 CIS countries with the highest share in foreign trade with Uzbekistan in 2023 (in million dollars, percent of total volume)⁴.

In terms of the volume and growth rate of foreign trade turnover in the regions of Uzbekistan, Tashkent city recorded a significant share, accounting for 38.8% of the total volume, or \$24.3 billion, while the smallest share was attributed to the Surkhandarya region, with 0.5%, or \$325.2 million.

Export of Uzbekistan:

The number of exporters reached 7,255, and the volume of exports of goods and services amounted to \$16.2 billion (excluding non-monetary gold), showing a 4.5% increase compared to the same period in 2022.

Export content:

- Goods: 78.8% (including industry – 16.6%);
- Food products and live animals: 7.3%;
- Machinery and transport equipment: 5.3%.

Among the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) and other foreign countries, Uzbekistan’s main export partners in 2023 were Russia (13.5%), China (10.1%), Kazakhstan (5.6%), Turkey (5.1%), Afghanistan (3.5%), Kyrgyzstan (2.6%), Tajikistan (2.5%), and other countries.

Among the twenty largest partner countries, Russia ranks first in terms of export volume and growth rate of goods and services, with a 5% increase. However, the shares of several other countries saw declines, including China with a 6.5% decrease, Kazakhstan with a 2.5% decrease, and Turkey with a 24% decrease. Additionally,

⁴ Source: <https://sputniknews.uz/20240123/ozbekiston-tashqi-savdo-aylanmasi-42169695.html>

Russia is the primary export market for fruits and vegetables, holding a 37% share, equivalent to 611.4 thousand tons (worth \$437.4 million), which is 2.2 times higher than exports to the second-ranked country, Pakistan. In 2023, Uzbekistan exported 639 types of textile products to 65 countries as part of its textile export initiatives.

Given these points, several recommendations can be made. First, it is essential to harmonize modernization efforts with export diversification to enhance the national economy's competitiveness, ensuring alignment with foreign market demands. In the process of modernizing the economy, improving national competitiveness by effectively attracting and utilizing direct investments is crucial. Moreover, developing and implementing national competitiveness criteria in line with both national and international standards is important. The systematic development of the real sector should also align with the processes of global economic integration.

Thus, Uzbekistan's harmonious economic development in conjunction with the global economy will provide a solid foundation for the country to establish a significant presence in international markets. This process requires constant attention and readiness for competition.

Conducting an effective diversification policy depends on how efficiently the relevant factors are applied in an enterprise's practical activities. Based on this, these factors have been systematically classified. However, many of these factors are difficult to quantify, complicating the calculation of their total value. This challenge creates the need to use modern methods for developing indicators that are suitable for the existing conditions.

In line with the objectives of this research, a comprehensive methodology for evaluating competitiveness has been proposed. This method represents the relative characteristics of an enterprise. The comprehensive assessment, derived from indicators of a more competitive enterprise, reflects the company's position in the competitive environment. This approach can serve as the main tool for measuring market share and analyzing changes in both the absolute and relative values of enterprise and product competitiveness.

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